

PROCESSES OF ASSIMILATION AND INTEGRATION IN THE INTERACTION OF CULTURES.

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the processes of interaction between cultures, their types and role in the life of representatives of different ethnic cultures.

Culture (from latin cultura - "cultivate, cultivate the land", from colere - "cultivate, tend") - a concept that has a huge number of meanings in various fields of human activity. Culture is a subject of study in philosophy, culturology, history, sociology, art history, linguistics (ethnolinguistics), political science, ethnology, psychology, economics, pedagogy.

Basically, culture is understood as human activity in its various manifestations, including all forms and ways of human self-expression and self-knowledge, accumulation of skills and abilities by man and society as a whole. Culture is also a manifestation of human subjectivity and objectivity (character, competence, skills, abilities and knowledge).

Ethnic culture is a set of ways of life inherent in an ethnic group, necessary for the preservation and development of the ethnic group.

The interaction of cultures, on the one hand, contributes to integration processes - the strengthening of contacts, the spread of bilingualism, the increase in the number of mixed marriages, and on the other hand, is accompanied by the strengthening of ethnic self-consciousness.

The ethnic processes of interaction at the ethnic level can lead to various forms of unification of ethnic groups and their cultures (assimilation, integration),

Assimilation processes, when members of an ethno-cultural entity lose their original culture and adopt a new one, are active in economically developed countries. Assimilation is carried out through conquest, mixed marriages, and a deliberate policy of dissolving a small people and culture into the environment of another larger ethnic group.

In this case it is possible:

- 1.unilateral assimilation, when a minority culture is completely displaced by the dominant culture under the pressure of external circumstances;
- 2.cultural mixing, when elements of majority and minority cultures mix, forming rather stable combinations;

3. Complete assimilation is a very rare phenomenon.

Usually there is a greater or lesser degree of transformation of the minority culture under the influence of the dominant culture. In this case there is a replacement of norms and values of culture, language, behavior, as a result of which the representatives of the assimilated group change their cultural identity. The number of mixed marriages is growing, minority representatives are included in all social structures of society.

Integration is the interaction within a country or any major region of several ethnic groups significantly different in language and culture, in which they have a number of common features, in particular elements of a common identity are formed, based on long-term economic, cultural interaction, political ties, but the peoples and cultures retain their identity.

In cultural studies integration is defined as the process of harmonization of logical, emotional, aesthetic values with cultural norms and actual behavior of people, as the establishment of functional interdependence between different elements of culture. In this regard, there are several forms of cultural integration:

- a) configurational, or thematic - integration based on similarity, on the basis of a common "theme" that sets the benchmark for human activity.
- b) stylistic - integration based on common styles - era, time, place, etc. Common styles (artistic, political, economic, scientific, philosophical, etc.) contribute to the formation of common cultural principles;
- c) logical - integration of cultures on the basis of logical coordination, bringing scientific and philosophical systems into a consistent state;
- d) connective - integration at the level of direct interconnection of the components of culture (cultures), carried out in direct contact between people;
- e) functional, or adaptive - integration in order to improve the functional efficiency of a person and the entire cultural community; characteristic of modernity: the world market, the world division of labor, etc;
- f) regulative - integration in order to settle or neutralize cultural and political conflicts.

Cultures in interaction do not simply complement each other, but enter into a complex relationship in which they mutually adapt by borrowing their best products. The changes brought about by these borrowings compel the people of a given culture to adapt, to adapt to them by absorbing and using these new elements in their lives. As a result, to a greater or lesser extent, the individual achieves compatibility with the new cultural environment. Both in the interaction of cultures and in the adaptation of an individual to the elements of the new culture, acculturation is believed to occur.

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